

NOSOVKA BREEDERS ACHIEVEMENTS: WINTER TRITICALE VARIETY SLAVETNE

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The morpho-biological and agroecological characteristics of the variety of the secondary triticale of winter Slavetne are presented and the elements of agrotechnology of cultivation of this variety in the different soil-climatic conditions of the country are highlighted.

The aim and tasks of the study. To study the morpho-biological and ecological properties of the triticale of the winter variety Slavetne on progressive elements of agrotechnology of cultivation in the conditions of the Eastern and Central Polissya, the transition zone Forest-Steppe-Polissya and the Central Forest-Steppe.

Material and methods. Studies on selection and ecological strain testing of the triticale of the Slavetne variety were carried out during 1998-2016. At the Nosovka selection and testing station (Chernihiv region), Bila Tserkva of the National Agrarian University and the Institute of Agriculture of Polesye of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine (Zhytomyr region).

Results and discussion. The ability of the winter triticale variety Slavetne to provide high yields in agroecosystems of the Eastern and Central Polissya, transition zone of Forest-Steppe-Polissya and Central Forest-Steppe of Ukraine is proved. The relatively high ecological stability of the triticale of the winter variety Slavetne to adverse environmental factors, the slow development at the onset of ontogenesis and its timely completion, contribute to a better resistance of plants to pests, pathogens of diseases, more effective use of winter-spring moisture and nutrients of soil. On the basis of the Slavetne variety by means of cross-stratification hybridization and further individual selection, promising lines ПС_1-12, ПС_2-12, ПС_6-12 were created and the frost-free line Slavetne polypshene.

Conclusions. In the conditions of the Eastern and Central Polissya, the transitional zone Forest-Steppe- Polissya and the Central Forest-Steppe of Ukraine, the grade of the triticale of winter wheat Slavetne is characterized as highly productive, high-yielding, resistant to unfavorable biotic and abiotic stresses of the environment.

Key words: *winter triticale, variety, morpho-biological and agroecological characteristics, yield and quality of grain, elements of agrotechnology for traditional and organic production.*